

LIMITLESS - LIght-weight MonItoring Tool for LargE Scale Systems

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This work presents LIMITLESS, a HPC framework that provides new strategies for monitoring clusters. LIMITLESS is a scalable light-weight monitor that is integrated with other HPC runtimes in order to obtain a holistic view of the system that combines both platform and application monitoring. This paper presents a description of the novel components of the architecture, including new approaches for reaching a higher scalability based on a combination of in-transit processing and performance prediction. We also include a methodology for improving application scheduling by means of machine learning classifiers and application profiling. This work also includes a practical evaluation on simulated and real platforms, that shows significant monitoring scalability, retrieving data capacity and reduced overheads. Results show that the performance prediction techniques reduce communications and the number of monitoring packets by more than 90% on average, and the fine-grain scheduling allows LIMITLESS to run applications in shared nodes reducing the makespan by 25% and saving resources.

Monitoring, application modelling, performance prediction, scheduling, machine learning.

0.1 Introduction

Currently, one of the key challenges in large-scale clusters is to determine as accurately as possible the status of the system every small fraction of time. There are two main approaches for obtaining this information: by means of the compute-node monitoring or by means of the analysis of the applications that running on the platform. The first one involves a system-wide monitoring infrastructure while the second one is usually restricted to the use of monitoring software executed with the applications. In this work we combine these two approaches in order to provide, not only a more accurate cluster monitoring, but also a scheme that permits to model the application behaviour in order to reduce the infrastructure monitoring overhead.

This work presents LIMITLESS, a highly-scalable monitor that is able to work under near-to-second sampling rates. LIMITLESS is fully integrated with other system software like the scheduler, CLARISSE and FlexMPI runtimes to enhance the monitor scalability. CLARISSE [1] is a middleware for data-staging coordination and control on large-scale HPC platforms that provides application I/O monitoring. FlexMPI [2] provides malleable capabilities to MPI applications and performs application CPU monitoring. In this way, the main contributions of this work are:

- An integration between LIMITLESS monitor and other runtimes for collecting application-related information.
- A novel analytic module for application performance modelling.
- A novel in-transit processing scalable feature for reducing the monitor traffic and the processing time.

Figure 1: General overview of the system architecture and interrelation with other components.

- A practical evaluation of the complete infrastructure on both simulated and real platforms.

The structure of the paper is as follows: Section 0.2 describes the architecture organization; Section 0.3 describes LIMITLESS’s features for providing monitoring scalability; Section 0.4 presents the different algorithms used to predict the immediate future state of the cluster; Section 0.5 provides a practical evaluation of the LIMITLESS monitor and the analytic tools provided; Section 0.6 shows relevant works related to our proposal. Finally, Section 0.7 summarizes the main conclusions and future work.

0.2 Monitor architecture

LIMITLESS is a light-weight scalable monitor that operates on each compute node and provides information about the platform resources and applications that are being executed. Figure 1 shows a general overview of how LIMITLESS is integrated with other system components like the application scheduler, FlexMPI and CLARISSE runtimes. As shown in this figure, LIMITLESS includes four main components: a *System monitor* that collects the performance metrics from the cluster, an *ElasticSearch* database [3] that provides persistent storage, Kibana, a *GUI* for displaying the cluster information in an user-friendly format, and an *Analytic* component that is used to analyse and model the executing applications.

Limitless Analytics (LAN) is the component that deals with the storage, visualization, communication with the scheduler and is the responsible of the performance prediction. It stores and manage the application models, generates the predictors, trains and executes the neural networks and the machine learning algorithms, and, in addition to that, the LAN component includes an API based on sockets for plugging other programs or modules, including user programs or other data visualizers.

When one application is executed, the scheduler notifies LIMITLESS Analytics (arrow 1) about the application characteristics (which is used to identify and classify the application). In a second step, when the applications are executed two different metrics are collected simultaneously: at node level to the monitor (arrow 2) and at application-level to FlexMPI and CLARISSE (arrow 3). Then, both metrics are processed by the respective runtimes and are written into Elastic search (arrows 4 and 5). Note that this process is concurrent. Then, the LIMITLESS analytics creates an application model using the information

stored in ElasticSearch (arrow 6). And finally, the prediction model (arrow 7) is sent to LIMITLESS in order to perform in-transit processing for reducing the network monitoring traffic. During all these processes, Kibana may be used to visualize (arrow 8) the cluster status.

0.2.1 System monitor

LIMITLESS includes a monitoring tool designed to provide performance information for generic purposes in large scale systems. One of its main interesting features is the possibility of change the monitoring period (also called *sample interval*) online, having one different for each node, and without the necessity of restart the system or the monitor. The monitoring interval can be set in a range of time from hours to seconds and also sub-second.

The System Monitor has been designed following the Tree-Based Overlays Network (TBON) [4] architecture. It offers simplicity and scalability, and allows the implementation of fault tolerance mechanisms. The monitor consists of one *LIMITLESS Daemon Monitor* (LDM) per node, which periodically collects the performance metrics; a set of *LIMITLESS DaeMon Aggregators* (LDAs), that forwards the information from the LDMS to other aggregators or servers; and the *LIMITLESS DaeMon Server* (LDS) that gathers and stores the monitoring information in ElasticSearch. Figure 2 shows a typical deployment of LIMITLESS with replication of the LDAs and LDSs. The purpose of replicating these components is to enhance the monitor scalability and resilience. The monitoring information collected by LIMITLESS includes different per-compute-node metrics related to CPU, GPU, cache memory, I/O, and network usage as well as energy consumption.

0.2.2 Monitoring policies

The monitoring policies specify how the performance metrics are collected by the LDS. There are two different alternatives: continuous monitoring and event-based monitoring. In the first one each LDM sends all metrics collected (usually in one network packet) every sample interval for obtaining an updated cluster status. The second one is not designed to provide a global vision of the cluster, but to notify events in certain compute nodes that are relevant or could harm the platform performance. We assume that an event occurs when a given performance metric (such as CPU energy usage) is above a certain user-defined threshold. Based on this, LDM will transmit only monitoring metrics that are bigger than the threshold. Note that this policy reduces the network traffic, as the system will only receive a notification when an event is produced, the LDS will reduce the related processing time. These notifications are displayed in the GUI and also sent to the scheduler, allowing to enhance the application scheduling [5].

Figure 2: Example of deployment with TMR and watchdog processes in the first monitoring branch.

0.2.3 Framework Deployment

Generic topologies can be used to deploy LIMITLESS. This permits to adapt the monitor deployment with the same topology as the cluster’s communication network. Figure 2 shows an example of a particular deployment with four compute-nodes per LDA, one LDA per LDS, and one ElasticSearch database (with a tree-based structure). In addition to the topological deployment, each component (for instance, a LDM) can be dynamically configured to adapt to the application characteristics (for instance, reducing the sampling interval in some nodes with a more variable workload) or to dynamically reconfigure the monitor connection topology.

0.2.4 Fault tolerance

LIMITLESS includes two different policies that are complementary: Triple Modular Redundancy (TMR) and Watchdogs. The first one allows the monitor components to be connected with a set of three different next-level components: each LDM is connected with three LDAs; each LDA is connected with another three LDAs and/or LDSs; and each LDS is connected with three ElasticSearch databases.

The watchdog policy provides resilience by launching each component with a service that checks whether the node works properly. In case of a component failure, the monitor will attempt to rerun the component with the same configuration. If this is not possible, the node is flagged as non-operational. Figure 2 shows the fault tolerance mechanisms in red colour. The dotted red lines show the triple module redundancy configuration for each node.

0.2.5 Data Storage and Visualization

ElasticSearch is used to store the data produced by the framework. Main features of ElasticSearch are high performance processing, its suitability for big

data storage, compression support and prebuilt data replications. Note that it is configured to deal efficiently with large network packets, so with this approach we aim to leverage this feature efficiently. Moreover, Elasticsearch is integrated with Kibana [6], an open-source scalable web interface for visual data representation. Kibana provides plugins to manage the data stored in the database, creating dashboards, performing time-series analysis and applying machine learning algorithms to the stored data.

0.2.6 CLARISSE and FlexMPI support

The execution framework shown in Figure 1 includes CLARISSE and FlexMPI runtimes. CLARISSE main goal is to provide control mechanisms through the I/O software stack in order to enhance the application I/O by means of coordinated policies. FlexMPI brings malleable capabilities to MPI applications that are able to dynamically increase or reduce the number of processes.

Both runtimes include libraries that are linked and executed with the application. These libraries that monitor the application I/O activity (by means of CLARISSE) and the application CPU and memory usage (by means of FlexMPI). The performance metrics are sent to the corresponding external controllers for CLARISSE and FlexMPI and subsequently are stored in Elasticsearch.

CLARISSE is used to detect interference between the applications that are running in the same node in order to move one to another node if I/O interference is detected. At the beginning of the execution of a certain application, the runtime collects the application performance metrics. Then, during the the rest of the execution, if the application suffers performance degradation (detected by analyzing the application performance metrics), then, there is some kind of interference.

The FlexMPI runtime is integrated with two objectives: the first one is to provide application migration capabilities (by means of malleability) from nodes with poor performance to nodes where they can run without interference (which is related to the CLARISSE’s objective of detecting performance degradation). The second one is to use the performance counters to provide more information about the system and the applications that are running. In this way, the system monitor provides two levels of data: information about the current performance of the real compute nodes (hardware level), and information about the performance of the applications that are running in the cluster (software level).

By means of this approach it is possible to include fine-grained information about the application characteristics. For instance, it is possible to record the duration of each I/O phase with a precision of milliseconds. This information will be used for carrying out a more precise application modelling that will be subsequently used by the monitor to improve the application scheduling process.

0.3 Scalable support

This section describes the three functionalities included in LIMITLESS for enhancing the monitoring scalability: optimized Data Packing, in-situ and in-transit processing. Optimized Data Packing is performed by the LDMs. In order to maximize the efficiency of this process, architecture-dependent features like the maximum packet length, are taken into account to optimally group different metrics into a single network packet by means of bit-level codifications that results in a significant reduction in the packet size.

Regarding the data packing, it is aimed to reduce the size of the packets sent. For example, in a basic monitoring (CPU, memory, one I/O interface, one network interface, and measuring cache hits and misses), a data packet has a size of 83 bytes. This packet contains both text and numeric data. The compression consists of building the packet transforming the numeric data into unsigned char, reducing the size to 1 byte of each metric (instead of 4 or 8 bytes). Then, the main server can decompress the packet obtaining the original values. With this method, the original packet currently has a size of 45 bytes. As LIMITLESS supports heterogeneous nodes, each node can use a different packet scheme based on its hardware configuration. At the beginning of the monitor execution, each node builds and sends its packet scheme to the LDS. After that, the LDS is able to parse each monitoring packet by mapping the packet values with scheme. Note that it is possible to dynamically change configurations related to the configuration of the components (sampling interval, destinations, fault-tolerance policies, etc.), but not the scheme of the monitoring packets (that require restarting the involved LDMs).

LDMs include in-situ processing algorithms [5] that analyse the captured metrics and selectively avoid transmitting them when the difference regarding the previous metrics is under a predefined threshold. By means of this approach, the amount of monitoring traffic related to a steady compute node can be reduced while guaranteeing a continuous monitoring of the system. Note that this algorithm is light-weight, given that it is executed in the same compute nodes as the applications. In [5] we have shown that by means of this approach it is possible to reduce up to the 87% of the metrics sent from the LDMs to the LDAs.

In-transit processing is based on using prediction algorithms in the LDA components. Figure 3 shows an example of this strategy which leverages the integration between LIMITLESS and scheduler for developing a prediction algorithm based on the application characteristics. For each new executing application, the scheduler notifies the monitor (arrow 1) the application name, input arguments and compute nodes that have been allocated. We denote it as *application context*. Based on that, a unique application ID is created and used for indexing all the performance metrics related to this execution. These metrics, along with the identifier and application context, are stored in Elastic Search.

In many cases, during the application development, the applications are executed several times with minor changes in its configuration. We call this col-

Algorithm 1 LIMITLESS in-transit pseudocode executed by the Analytic components. A_i stands for the application context of application i -th. E is the ensemble related to the application. P_i stands for the application’s performance predictor.

```

1: // Limitless Analytic
2: INPUT (from scheduler):  $A_i$ 
3:  $E = get\_ensemble(A_i)$ 
4: if  $E == \emptyset$  then
5:    $E = create\_ensemble(A_i)$ 
6: else
7:    $P_i = generate\_predictor(m_i, E)$ 
8:    $send\_predictor(P_i)$ 
9: end if

```

lection of executions *application ensemble*. Note that the executions belonging to the same ensemble have similar characteristics, like the duration of the CPU and communication phases, or the I/O access pattern. LIMITLESS includes an *Analytic component* that is able to identify the application ensemble related to each new executing application. This is done by comparing the application execution context with the existing ones stored in Elastic Search. Algorithm 1 shows the Analytic component pseudocode. For every newly executed application A_i the related ensemble is obtained (line 3). If it doesn’t already exist, a new one is created (line 5). Otherwise, once the ensemble is identified, the Analytic component compares (line 7) the collected application metrics with the ones related to previous executions (that are stored in Elastic Search). If they are similar (in terms of duration of the CPU, communication and I/O phases) a predictor is generated taking into account both the current and previous executions. This predictor is sent (line 8) to the LDAs and LDSs involved in the application execution¹.

Figure 3 illustrates an overview of this process for an application (denoted as App) that is executed several times. We denote A_i with $i = 1, \dots, n$ each one of the related execution context i . When the application is executed for the first time, a new application ensemble is created, $E = \{A_1\}$. Then, before starting the second execution, the related application context sent by the scheduler (arrow 1) permits the Analytic component to identify if it belongs to any existing ensemble E based on the Elastic Search records (arrow 2), which is properly updated $E = \{A_1, A_2\}$ and the generated model is created and sent to the corresponding LDAs and LDS (arrow 3). When the application is executed, the LDAs compare the incoming metrics (arrow 4) from the LDM with the ones predicted by the model (arrow 5). If the metrics are the same (within a given threshold), these metrics are not sent (arrow 6) because the LDS is able to generate them (arrow 7) using the previous model.

¹Note that the specific list of LDAs and LDSs related to the application is obtained from the scheduler which determines the specific compute nodes where the application is executed.

Algorithm 2 LIMITLESS in-transit pseudocode executed by the LDA. P_i stands for the i -th application’s performance predictor.

```

1: // Limitless DaeMon Aggregator (LDA)
2: INPUT (from analytics):  $P_j, j = 1, \dots, N_{app}$ 
3: while TRUE do
4:   for ( $i = 0; i < N_{app}; i++$ ) do
5:      $m_i = get\_metrics(A_i)$ 
6:     if  $P_i == \emptyset$  then
7:        $send\_metrics(m_i)$ 
8:     else
9:        $n_i = generate\_metrics(P_i)$ 
10:      if  $||n_i - m_i|| < threshold$  then
11:         $do\_nothing$ 
12:      else
13:         $send\_metrics(m_i)$ 
14:      end if
15:    end if
16:  end for
17: end while

```

Figure 3: LIMITLESS - Network traffic reduction due to modelling and prediction.

Algorithm 2 shows the logic related to the LDAs. When the A_2 execution starts, the performance metrics are collected (line 5). If the performance predictor does not exist, then the metrics are sent to the LDS (line 7). Otherwise, the metrics are compared with the generated ones by the model (line 10). If they are the same (within some limits), they are not sent to the LDS (line 11) saving network traffic. In the other case, the predictor fails to reproduce the application behaviour. Consequently, the prediction is overridden, and the metrics are sent to the LDS (line 13) until a more accurate model is generated.

Algorithm 3 shows the logic related to the LDSs. The basic idea behind this algorithm is that if the prediction fails in the LDAs, performance metrics should arrive from these components. In this way, the LDSs waits for incoming metrics (line 5). If they arrive, they are taken and stored in Elastic Search (lines 6 and 7). Otherwise, the metrics are generated using the model and stored (lines 9 and 10). Note that the performance prediction P_i used by the LDAs and LDSs is the same.

Algorithm 3 LIMITLESS in-transit pseudocode executed by the LDS. P_i stands for the i -th application’s performance predictor.

```

1: // Limitless DaeMon Server (LDS)
2: INPUT (from analytics):  $P_j, j = 1, \dots, N_{app}$ 
3: while TRUE do
4:   for ( $i = 0; i < N_{app}; i++$ ) do
5:     if  $new\_metrics(A_i)$  then
6:        $m_i = get\_metrics(A_i)$ 
7:        $write\_metrics(m_i)$ 
8:     else
9:        $n_i = generate\_metrics(P_i)$ 
10:       $write\_metrics(n_i)$ 
11:    end if
12:  end for
13: end while

```

Algorithm 4 Application performance model logic based on pattern matching. Variables n_i and m_i corresponds, respectively, to the i^{th} measured and recorded performance metrics.

```

1: // Limitless Analytic
2: INPUT (from Elastic search):  $m_i$ 
3:  $\{n_i\} = ES\_read\_metrics(i)$ 
4: if  $\|n_i - m_i\| < threshold$  then
5:    $n_{i+1} = ES\_read\_metrics(i + 1)$ 
6:    $return(n_{i+1})$ 
7: else
8:    $return("Prediction failed")$ 
9: end if

```

0.4 Performance prediction techniques

This section describes the different algorithms used to predict the immediate future state of the cluster. The idea of this component is to leverage the large amount of data that LIMITLESS collects for predicting the future behaviour of the applications and reducing the communication between the monitored compute nodes and the aggregators. A second goal consists of enhancing the application scheduling by means of identifying applications that be executed in the same compute node without degrading their performance. We have used three different prediction techniques based on single-variable analysis (application pattern matching, prediction based on historical window, and classification based on neural networks) and one based on multi-variable correlation (based on different machine learning classification and searching algorithms).

The first technique (depicted in Algorithm 4) is based on pattern generation. This solution stores the performance metrics as a pattern during an execution of an application. In next executions, each collected metric is compared with the corresponding metric in the pattern. If the difference is below a given threshold,

then the following metric is generated from the next recorded one. Otherwise, the model fails to provide a prediction. This model is lightweight and works well with applications that exhibit the same execution pattern in different executions.

The second technique corresponds to a short-time predictor based on a sample-window. This algorithm predicts the performance values based on the interpolation of a certain number of previous values. The size of the set used in the interpolation is proportional to the size of the window. For instance, a window of size 5 uses the last recorded five samples to compute the interpolation and produce each prediction. Note that this approach works well for periodic applications with different phases (CPU, communication, I/O), where the length of the phases is similar during the execution and there are little variations in the performance metrics during each phase. The main different aspect of the first solution is the utilization of an interpolation algorithm that is used to refine the predicted values, instead of using directly the next pattern value.

The third technique uses neural networks to learn the application behaviour from data coming from many previous executions and to predict the immediate states when a known application is deployed. We have used one neural network per application which is trained with the monitor data of the application ensemble. Each neural network is composed of three layers with 120, 60 and 1 neurons respectively. The training starts when the first application of a given ensemble is performed. After that, each network is capable of adjusting its weights to recognize the application pattern. The second application execution is used to assess the accuracy of the prediction. If it is not accurate enough, further executions are used to provide more training data. Note that the main advantage of this approach is that it is not necessary to use historical values for making a prediction.

The last prediction technique is based on a multi-variable correlation using the machine learning algorithms. The first studied algorithm is *Nearest Neighbour* (NN) [7,8], then the solution is extended with *AdaBoost* and *Support Vector Machine* algorithms due to their accuracy in the analysis, which will be described in Section 0.5, although other algorithms have been also tested.

In this approach, given a set of k performance metrics collected by a LDM in a current sample, our solution predicts the application performance and uses this information for two different actions: to reduce the network communication between the monitor components and to improve the application scheduling. The main idea behind the second goal is to obtain the application profile using the monitor and then, use this information for predicting the application performance when it is executed in the same node with other applications. Executing applications concurrently in the same nodes aims to optimize the resource utilization by leveraging the computational resources (cores) not used by one of the applications. It can result in less energy utilization (given that less compute nodes may be used). In case of large workloads, it contributes to reduce the overall makespan reduction and increase the platform throughput because the system has more compute nodes available to run extra applications. However, running multiple applications in the same compute node may produce performance degradation due to contention in the sharing of the compute node's

resources between applications with different characteristics. We call this effect *application interference*. For this reason, this decision (sharing or not the compute node) has to be taken based on the application characteristics. In this work, we will leverage monitoring information to determine that application interference does not occur.

For the first goal, an algorithm capable of predicting the following performance metrics is enough, and we use NN. Having the set of k metrics, this algorithm finds the most similar k -metrics to this set in the complete historical data. Then, the following recorded ones are provided as a prediction. Note that this algorithm is able to make predictions using very large datasets (like the historical records related to an application ensemble) with low overhead. The idea behind this approach is to leverage the similarity between different metrics belonging to the same application ensemble to make a prediction.

For the second goal, it is not enough to predict the state of the cluster, but we also need information about the application profile that distinguishes its execution phases. That is, we need fine-grained monitoring. For this reason, we use support for machine learning classification algorithms. The idea includes three steps: running concurrently two applications to know if there is application interference. Then, if it happens, dividing the application models into different phases that will be recognizable by the classification algorithms. Once these phases are identified, and the profile of each one (CPU-intensive, communications-intensive, etc.) is known, the phases of different applications that do not generate interference can be combined, allowing to run in the same compute node to maximize the machine resource utilization. Algorithm 5 shows the general algorithm pseudocode for this *fine-grain scheduling algorithm*, which consists of the study and schedule the phases of applications, instead of their complete execution. This technique allows LIMITLESS to combine long-time with short-time execution applications depending on the profile of their phases. The scheduler, for each application ready to be executed, sends a notification to the LAN component (Line 1) and obtains the related application model (Line 2). Then, the LAN component obtains the list of the running applications from the scheduler (Line 4). For each one, it identifies its model, profile and phases (Line 5). The next step consists of evaluating if there is interference between the models of the application ready to run and the currently running. If there is no interference between two applications (Line 6) and there are enough available resources in the same compute node, then the LAN component uses the same node for running the new application (Line 7). However, if interference is detected or there are not enough resources, then the LAN component requests to allocate app_k in a new node. Finally, in Line 13 the LAN notifies the scheduler which is the compute node where application app_k should be executed.

0.5 Evaluation

The evaluation (except the subsection 0.5.1) has been done both by simulation and in a physical platform that consists of eight compute nodes divided in two

Algorithm 5 Fine-grained scheduling algorithm. Variable app_k represents a given application k that may be in execution or ready for being executed. $\mathbb{M}app_k$ represents the application model used by the Analytic component, and $node_k$ is the compute node where the application is being executed.

```

1: for each  $app_k$  in Ready_Queue do
2:    $\mathbb{M}app_k = model(app_k, AdaBoost, SVM)$ 
3:    $node_k = \emptyset$ 
4:   for each  $app_j$  in Execution do
5:      $\mathbb{M}app_j = model(app_j, AdaBoost, SVM)$ 
6:     if  $interference(\mathbb{M}app_k, \mathbb{M}app_j) == FALSE$  then
7:        $node_k = request\_node(app_j)$ 
8:     end if
9:   end for
10:  if  $node_k == \emptyset$  then
11:     $node_k = request\_new\_node()$ 
12:  end if
13:   $execute(app_k, node_k)$ 
14: end for

```

racks. The cluster contains two nodes with Intel(R) Xeon(R) E5 with 8 cores and 256GB of RAM in one rack and six nodes with Intel(R) Xeon(R) E7 with 12 cores and 128GB of RAM in the other. The connection between nodes in the same rack is a 10 Gbps Ethernet, whilst the connection between racks is made through a 1 Gbps Ethernet. The I/O is based on Gluster parallel file system.

0.5.1 Scalability evaluation

This subsection describes the overhead and scalability analysis. The overhead of the LDMs depends on the sampling interval, which is user-defined. In our experiments we have tested the LDMs with a minimum sampling interval of one second, which produces less than 1.0% of CPU and consumption with a memory footprint of 3890 KB in resident memory. These overheads are obtained from the system performance counters. Moreover, we have executed several times the same application quantify the variability in the monitoring data. On average, the execution lasts 9801.6 seconds and 9801.8 seconds when the monitor is active or not. We have also executed a CPU application (use case one in subsection 0.5.2) five times with and without the monitor. On average, the application lasts 37620.86 seconds with the monitor active and 37620.25 seconds without it.

Note that LDMs are executed in the same compute nodes as the applications, so this overhead should be kept as low as possible. The LDAs and LDS use more computational resources than the LDMs. Note that these components are supposed to be executed in nodes not exclusively used by the applications or with more resources than the standard compute nodes. These two modules are in charge of receiving, processing and re-transmitting the performance metrics provided by LDMs. For this reason, the main sources of overhead for them are both the CPU and the network traffic (especially with reduced sampling

Figure 4: LIMITLESS - Scalability analysis: CPU overhead and percentage of monitoring packet loss.

intervals).

We have carried out different experiments for evaluating the monitor-related CPU consumption and the percentage of packet lost in order to evaluate the monitor overhead and analyze the monitor scalability. This study has been done on a real platform with 60 compute nodes (960 cores) under real workloads (i.e. during the monitor evaluation the cluster was in production mode). Note that in this configuration the workload of each core was independently monitored. Figure 4 shows the average CPU overhead and the ratio of packet loss for each configuration (different number of cores that have been monitored). The results show that the CPU overhead linearly increases until 320 cores. Then, the overhead continues to increase at a smaller rate. Note that monitoring server is multi-threaded and the processing threads are created on-demand, when number of monitoring packets increases (i.e. more nodes/cores are monitored). In the current configuration, the maximum number of processing threads is 16 (the server node consists of an Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2630L v3 @ 1.80GHz with 16 cores). This number is reached when 320 cores are monitored. In the figure we can observe that for cores below this number, the main overhead source is the creation and execution of new processing threads. For values above this number, the overhead increase is related to a higher workload related to each existing thread. The packet loss ratio keeps under a background level of less than 1%. The reason behind this is that LIMITLESS sends the information using UDP packets, and there exists a certain loss rate when the platform is under medium/high loads. On average, the packet loss ratio is 0.59% with a standard deviation of 0.53%.

To estimate the scalability limit, we have simulated a cluster with OM-NET++ [9] under different workloads. The simulated architecture corresponds to a simple deployment: n nodes (with one IO and network interface, and without GPU, that execute LDM functions) connected to a switch, and the switch connected to another node (that represents LDS). The connection be-

tween nodes and the switch is 1Gbps Ethernet. When we consider a particular computational-intensive configuration of LIMITLESS consisting of a sampling interval of one second and a single-thread implementation of the LDAs and LDS². Under these circumstances in our experiments each LDA and LDS are able to be connected at the same time with 200 other components (either LDMs or LDAs). Consequently, one LDA in the first aggregation level is able to gather the metrics of 200 nodes, and one LDA in the second aggregation level could manage 40,000 nodes. Note that the packet size used for sending each sample ranges from 64 to 1024 bytes, according to the number of metrics collected by each LDM. Assuming that a sampling interval of 1 second and 40,000 nodes, the related bandwidth would range between 2.4Mbit/s and 39Mbit/s, much smaller than the typical bandwidth values of the network, like 10Gbit/s. Besides, note that the monitoring infrastructure could use the service network existing in many clusters producing no-overhead in the communication fabric.

0.5.2 Smart analytic evaluation

In our experiments, we have considered four different use cases. The first use corresponds to a parallel implementation Jacobi method written in MPI that alternates CPU, communication and I/O phases. Jacobi is executed using 8 processes with a matrix size of 15,000 entries. Given that the application is executed exclusively most of the time in one compute node, the duration of each phase is approximately constant during all the execution. Figure 5a shows four main performance metrics collected during the execution of Jacobi: CPU, memory, I/O and network usage (as a percentage). The spikes show a reduction in the CPU usage and corresponds to the communication phases which are performed periodically. There is sharp increase in the CPU use around t=25,000 sec. that corresponds to another application running in the same compute node for a while.

The second use case corresponds to the simultaneous execution of two Jacobi applications that are exclusively executed in different nodes. Because of that, the duration of the CPU and communication phases is barely constant, but the communication phase duration changes when both applications perform that communication at the same time. In this case, there is an interference that make that the network bandwidth would be shared by both applications, increasing the phase duration. Figure 6a shows the four main performance metrics corresponding to this use case. The use case uses 12 processes, consuming nearly 100% of the computer node's CPU. Now the distance between the spikes related to the I/O is not constant because of the network interference .

The third use case corresponds to BTIO from NAS Parallel Benchmarks configured as class C. This benchmark alternates CPU and I/O phases. Figure 7a shows the main collected metric during the benchmark execution.

Finally, the fourth use case corresponds to EpiGraph, which is an agent-based epidemic tool for simulating the propagation of influenza and COVID-19

²Note that in the latest version of LIMITLESS the LDS is multithreaded which considerably improves the performance.

viruses. EpiGraph was developed using MPI and alternates multiple CPU and communication phases. The intensity of each phase depends on the number of the infected individuals in every simulation stage. Figure 8a shows the main performance metrics for this application when six MPI processes are running. The CPU is approximately constant but as it will be described in section 0.5.3, the communication time is not. An example of a use case 1 execution can be seen in Figure 8a, which shows how all metrics reproduce phases.

With the aim of considering a broad number of application profiles, we have included different classes of application behaviours ranging from repetitive CPU and I/O profiles (Jacobi, BT-IO and MG) to evolving profiles (EpiGraph). Note that all of them represent real-work application profiles.

Table 1 shows the accuracy of each predictor for the four considered use cases using the performance metrics collected by LIMITLESS. This accuracy is expressed as a percentage of correct predictions. We used a tolerance value of 3% in each predictor. When we compare both executions of Jacobi method (use cases 1 and 2), the predictors are in general more accurate for the first use case because it has a steadier behaviour. The performance metrics collected from EpiGraph are approximately constant which make the predictions be accurate with this application. The only exception is the network usage which shows different phases, including variations around 15% in its values. Note that the amount of saved LDA network traffic is proportional to the predictor accuracy given that each correct prediction avoids sending one monitoring sample to the LDS. This optimization also reduces the load in the LDS, because there are less monitoring packets to process.

Note that the key idea of this approach is that both LDA and LDS execute the same predictor configured by the Analytic component. The predictors based on pattern matching and historical window have no input parameters, thus there is no transmission overhead. The parameters related to the neural network have a size of 28 KB whereas the ones related to the multi-variable correlation using the Nearest Neighbour Machine Learning algorithm have a size of 23 KB.

Table 2 shows the accuracy of each predictor for the use cases one, two and four using the performance metrics collected by CLARISSE and FlexMPI and stored in ElasticSearch. It was not possible to integrate Btio in CLARISSE nor FlexMPI because it is written in Fortran. EpiGraph is integrated in both runtimes, although in this paper we neither use malleability nor I/O scheduling with this application. Note that these runtimes use timestamps for recording the duration of the CPU, communication and I/O phases. This brings a more accurate representation of the application that enhances the modelling. As we can see in Table 2 the accuracy of the prediction algorithms is improved.

In summary, all these optimizations have an impact on reducing the number of packets sent by the monitor. It produces two results. The first one is that the network traffic is reduced between the LDAs and the LDSs. The second one is the reduction of the number of packets received in the LDSs, which decreases the computational resources used to process the incoming monitoring packets.

Figure 5: Jacobi - Use case 1 with four main metrics: CPU usage, memory consumption, I/O and network usage.

Figure 6: Jacobi method with interference - Use case 2 with four main metrics: CPU usage, memory consumption, I/O and network usage.

0.5.3 Scheduling based on monitoring

This section describes how LIMITLESS uses the data collected and the machine-learning classification features to support our new scheduling technique called *fine-grain scheduling*.

In this case, we present four use cases, which consist of combining the execution of EpiGraph, which executes 6 processes, with N -MG benchmarks that execute six processes, which are memory-intensive and performs long and short-distance communications, for 100 seconds. The difference between these use cases is the infection propagation: the use cases one and three simulates one COVID-19 infection wave for Spain in 2020, and the use cases two and four two COVID-19 infection waves (see Figure 9) for Spain in 2021. The figure represents the number of infections for each one wave using a small scenario of a city with 500,000 inhabitants. These represent the execution takes around 2950 seconds, and Figures 10 and 11 show the communication usage during each execution. This communication is expressed as KB per second (input and output), and it shows the communication pattern of each use case. Note that the communication pattern is strongly correlated with the infection curves: when the number of infections increases, EpiGraph becomes more cpu-intensive, and

Figure 7: BT-IO - Use case 3 with four main metrics: CPU usage, memory consumption, I/O and network usage.

Figure 8: EpiGraph - Use case 1 with four main metrics: CPU usage, memory consumption, I/O and network usage.

the communication intensity decreases. On the other hand, when there are less infections, the simulator performs less computations, and the communication phases are executed more frequently, increasing the communication intensity.

The aims of this strategy are (1) to detect when EpiGraph is running in a certain node, and (2) detect the current execution phase. With this information, that can be acquired from the monitoring data and machine learning algorithms used by the LAN component, the scheduler can run instances of MG when there is no interference with EpiGraph. Note that this profiling process is done offline when there is enough data about applications, and some classification algorithms used to identify phases and applications can be seen in 3, including the accuracy in our experiments. Besides, these tests have been performed in two nodes with 12 cores with *Hyperthreading*. We have decided to do not use this feature and limit the maximum number of processes (of EpiGraph and MGs) to 12 per node. This is why the combined executions CPU use is 50% instead of 100%.

Based on the profile of each application, EpiGraph and MG suffer interference when the first one increases its communications. The cause is that the first one makes more communications when the number of infected people decreases. However, MG is constant in CPU and communication intensities, and the interference becomes important when EpiGraph generates that peaks of network

Figure 9: Distribution of the number of infections with COVID-19 during EpiGraph simulation for use cases 1 and 2.

usage. This behaviour can be seen in Figure 12 shows how EpiGraph increases MG’s iteration times when EpiGraph’s iteration times are shorter (note that smaller iteration times for EpiGraph means larger communication intensities). Figure 13 shows the same but in a use case with one bigger wave. As it can be seen in these cases, both applications run concurrently generating an important degradation between them: the degradation is 32.5% for the first case, and 32.2% for the second. Detecting when EpiGraph performs low-intensity communication phases allows LIMITLESS to run MG tasks during that phases, using the information of the predictors. The scheduler will execute MG during the peaks of the infection propagation and EpiGraph will be exclusively executed during the periods with low COVID-19 incidence, that is when the communication frequency reaches the maximum values.

Executing these use cases in a two compute node means that the applications will run at the same time. However, the second compute node will run exclusively instances of MG (the number depends on the scheduling and the compatible phases). The first use case is executed with 14 MG instances as a workflow. The second one is executed with 12 MG instances as a workflow.

	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4
Pattern matching	25.2%	25.2%	24.7%	81%
Historical window	61.5%	82.7%	50.0%	76.0%
Neural networks	99.5%	93.3%	98.0%	95.8%
Machine Learning	90.8%	90.5%	88.5%	99,8%

Table 1: Accuracy of the different prediction algorithms for the four use cases expressed as percentage of correct predictions.

Figure 10: EpiGraph use case 1 - Communication during the execution which shows two waves.

Finally, the last two use cases are executed with 25 MG instances. As it can be seen in Figure 14 for use case 1, Figure 15 for use case 2, Figure 16 for use case 3 and Figure 17 for use case 4. Combining different executions of different applications, when there is no interference between them, decreases the use of the computational resources. In all the figures, the execution of MG instances can be noticed when the CPU of the machine increases from 25% to 50%. Note that figures 15 and 17 are similar because the node 1 does not change respect the second use case. The second node (not shown in the figure) runs the instances of MG exclusively when it is not possible to run them in the same node as EpiGraph. Note that the number of the instances executed in the second node depends on the current execution stage of EpiGraph (whether it creates interference or not) and the remaining MG instances that have to be executed. In the considered scenario these numbers (instances of MG executed in exclusively in the second compute node) are 9 for the first use case, zero for the second, 15 for the third, and 12 for the last one.

The combination of both applications produces between 2.1% and 2.4% of performance degradation in the four use cases. It is caused by the overlap of MG with some CPU phases of EpiGraph due to the precision in identifying the execution phase. LIMITLESS uses a voting process between the machine

	Jacobi excl.	Jacobi interf.	EpiGraph
Pattern matching	48.5%	53.2%	95.4%
Historical window	98.6%	98.7%	99.2%
Neuronal networks	99.3%	99.5%	99.5%
Machine Learning	98.7%	98.8%	99.3%

Table 2: Accuracy of the different prediction algorithms using FlexMPI and Clarisse as inputs.

Figure 11: EpiGraph use case 2 - Communication during the execution which shows one wave.

Figure 12: Use case 1 - Relation between EpiGraph and MG when they are executed in the same node at the same time (two waves).

learning classifiers to validate each phase identification. As this process is not 100% accurate, it is possible to obtain certain interference degree.

The results are summarized in Table 4 that shows the computational resources used on each use case, expressed as total CPU time used. The first column of the table shows the results when different exclusive nodes are used for EpiGraph and MG, i.e., each application are executed separately. Note that in this case not all the cores of each compute node are used. For instance, in the first use case, the accumulated CPU time (52,200 seconds) will be equal to 12 times the use time of the first compute node (used by EpiGraph) plus 12 times the use time of the second compute node (used by MG instances), where 12 is the number of cores in each node. When fine-grained scheduling is enabled, some MG instances are executed in the same node as EpiGraph (compute node 1) decreasing the utilization of the second node. This leads to a reduction in the accumulated CPU time to 46,200 seconds. As it can be seen, the *fine-grained* scheduling allows the system to take advantage of the unused resources existing in a node improving the system utilization.

Figure 13: Use case 2 - Relation between EpiGraph and MG when they are executed in the same node at the same time (one wave).

Figure 14: Use case 1 (Node 1) result combining EpiGraph and MG when LIMITLESS detects compatible phases between both applications.

0.6 Related work

System monitoring for large-scale HPC platforms is a complex task, which becomes increasingly challenging as the scale and complexity of the infrastructure increases [5]. In the context of system monitors, we can find solutions like Ganglia [10], one of the most-used monitoring tools for HPC systems. One of its main features is that all the nodes receive information from the others. One drawback of this solution is that the fault tolerance mechanisms that use increase the communication and processing overhead and the amount of replicated information. Another similar tool is Collectd [11], which is a daemon that collects system and application performance metrics. Its main strength is that it has a low overhead. However, it only collects and stores the monitor metrics in the form of raw data. The user has to gather, manage and process the collected information. The authors in [12] present a monitoring system for HPC systems that shows an architecture similar to LIMITLESS. Their approach relies on classifying the monitoring metrics based on individual needs and on

Figure 15: Use case 2 (Node 1) result combining EpiGraph and MG when LIMITLESS detects compatible phases between both applications.

Figure 16: Use case 3 (Node 1) result combining EpiGraph and MG when LIMITLESS detects compatible phases between both applications.

aggregating messages to improve the communication from the nodes to the root component. Both monitors have the same architecture based on Tree-Based Overlay Networks, and it offers simplicity, scalability, and fault tolerance. Regarding this last feature, this work performs data replication in a 2x factor, and LIMITLESS uses Triple Modular Redundancy with two possible configurations: with and without redundancy. Regarding the performance and overhead, both alternatives provide similar results. However, the generated data is different because this work classifies the monitoring metrics using a predefined format for each compute node (it is not mentioned in the ork whether the scheme can be adapted to heterogeneous platforms or not). On the other hand, in LIMITLESS each LDM creates its own scheme that the LDS receives at the beginning of the execution.

Application performance monitoring in large scale systems is an important

Figure 17: Use case 4 (Node 1) result combining EpiGraph and MG when LIMITLESS detects compatible phases between both applications.

topic to enhance applications performance and to maximize system usage. Many applications exhibit a performance that changes among the time, thus some authors [13] have focused on making dynamic application profiling based on system monitoring. The usual technique is to collect system metrics and sending the information to a central component through a hierarchical model. Then, different algorithms are used to extract the knowledge about the application behaviour and to elaborate application profiles that are subsequently used to guide different components, like the scheduler. Izadpanah et al. [14] propose an optimization in the architecture of the monitoring systems based on integrating streaming capabilities to transmit and process the dynamically collected data. As a use case the authors focus on discovering and assessing contention in shared parallel file systems. Lustre is a popular shared parallel file system utilized broadly on HPC systems, and the objective is to detect contention for both meta-data services and read and write bandwidth. The results show that the monitor is able to detect I/O contention in different scenarios under different loads. The idea is to improve the data processing capabilities whilst keeping low the overhead and latencies related to the monitoring agents. To achieve these objectives, the opti-

Algorithm	60 s.	100 s.
AdaBoost	45%	75.6%
ANBC	31.1%	45.8%
BAG	34.5%	56.9%
MinDistance.	45.8%	80.7%
SVM	86.9%	100%

Table 3: Accuracy of the different classification algorithms using patterns of 60 and 100 seconds of EpiGraph.

mization consists of using data streams between the monitoring components in order to send the data efficiently and transform them to extract the meaningful information in a distributed way. This is the main difference between this related work and our proposal. The optimization proposed in this work leverages the aggregation points on the compute platform to process the data where the performance impact is not an issue. However, the authors do not clarify if these aggregation points are dedicated nodes or not and if they are defined statically or can be dynamically configured. LIMITLESS performs similar actions, taking into account that the aggregator nodes could be dedicated and non-dedicated, performing more or fewer transformations to the data depending on it.

In [15] the authors propose Wintermute, a framework that enables online Operational Data Analytics (ODA) on large-scale HPC systems. They provide this ODA on top of a widely-used monitoring system: DCDB. The objective of ODA is to analyze the operation of an HPC system to gain insight into its behaviour, which can be used to implement a proactive control process that auto-manages the system in certain situations. Due to the amount of information associated with the monitoring process, Wintermute includes heuristics and machine learning algorithms in the same way as LIMITLESS does. Besides, this related work is interesting because the decisions taken are based on a survey. Due to this, the architecture has been designed to fulfil some requirements such as flexibility, scalability, modularity, etc. The result is a plugin for monitoring tools that provides ODA features with a negligible overhead.

Other example of application monitoring based on system monitoring is [16], where the authors developed a system that parses the Slurm log file and extracts the information, generating reports for the users. LIKWID [17] is a framework that performs job or task monitoring. Its architecture is similar to LIMITLESS because its model is based on a monitor (Diamond), a non-SQL database (influxDB) and a visualizer (Grafana). The difference is that this solution is oriented to small and medium-sized clusters while LIMITLESS includes more scalable features, combines monitoring in two levels (system and application) and includes different features to reduce network traffic and perform application modelling.

In a different area, there are works that combine monitoring with machine-

U.C.	CPU time (s)	CPU time (s)	Saved resources
	Exclusive nodes	Fine-grained scheduling	%
1	52200	46200	11.5
2	49800	35400	28.9
3	65400	53400	19.4
4	65400	49800	23.9

Table 4: Execution summary of the use cases. Accumulated CPU time for each use case and scheduling.

learning techniques. Yu et al. [18] present a paper that combines network monitoring with prediction techniques to design a cross-layer security algorithms for intrusion detection. Rashti et al. [19] uses prediction models in order to reduce the power consumption of a wireless sensor network. Tang et al. [20] proposed a similar work to predict a bridge monitoring data based on regressions using support vector machine. Xiaobing et al. [21] made a study of the historical data of a gas tunnel to predict the gas emission tendency based on monitor data. This work includes a detailed methodology description and an exhaustive evaluation of the prediction accuracy.

A similar work, but adapted to transmission line sag, is presented in [22]. The main difference with the previous one is that here an online monitoring is used to give short-term sag prediction. In [23] the authors presented a method to make prediction using the Nearest Neighbour Algorithm to make predictions using an unprocessed dataset, so that the algorithm could be adapted to any kind of monitoring data, potentially providing good predictions.

Authors in [24] introduce a novel technique to identify the running applications in HPC systems: Taxonomist. The architecture of their proposal includes a monitoring tool that collects statistical metrics from the applications and a methodology to post-process the collected data to generate application patterns. These patterns will be used later to identify if a running application has been executed before or not. Notet that determining which metrics are most appropriate to identify the applications is a complex task. However, the proposal is based on some statistical variables that the authors have identified by means of supervised machine learning algorithms. The authors delegate the monitoring task to the monitoring tool installed in the platform that is used. However, in our case, LIMITLESS includes a lightweight monitoring tool that can be easily adapted to each use case (e.g. different hardware, components, metrics to collect, etc.). However, the methodology to process the collected information is similar in both of them: both alternatives need at least one execution of each application to start identifying them, and use machine learning algorithms to classify and identify the applications. Besides, Taxonomist and LIMITLESS include a confidence threshold to avoid false positives. If none of the confidence calculated values are above a determined confidence threshold, Taxonomist marks the application as *unknown*. On the other side, LIMITLESS compares the previously generated models for each application to find which one that is the most similar. The application is identified if the current pattern has a similarity above 90%. Finally, it is important to mention that Taxonomists removes the monitoring data from the beginning and the end of the executions. The idea is to suppress the initialization and finalization phases. However, LIMITLESS currently does not do include this enhancement, that may be related to the lower precision of the identification and prediction algorithms that LIMITLESS obtains.

In [25] the authors present a new machine learning algorithm that combines Random Forest algorithm with a modified AdaBoost algorithm to classify tumours from the MRI Brain tissues. The medical images are the input for Random Forest and AdaBoost to improve the accuracy of the classification. ANBC

algorithms have been used in [26] to train offline foot contact detection and perform analysis in real-time. The authors obtain an accuracy around 95%, which means that this algorithm works well in real-time environments. Other studies work with Softmax algorithm and others, as [27] conclude that this algorithm works well with datasets that are linearly separable. In [28–31] different studies based on machine learning algorithms like *BAG and Random Forest*, *Decision Tree*, *HMM* and *DTW* are shown. This work includes a description of the different algorithms, the results, and comparisons between other solutions using different datasets. Note that all of these related works train the algorithms offline and use meta-algorithms to create better datasets. Using this information is possible to adapt our algorithms to the datasets depending on the strengths of each one. [32] describes how to use the KNN classifier to detect potential COVID-19 infected patients. This algorithm is interesting because of its simplicity and the accuracy reached when working with datasets without noise. For multi-dimensional datasets, [33] describes how to adapt GMM classifier to identify different features in the speech in different languages. This solution is an alternative of NN used in this work. Finally, in [34] the authors describe an approach that integrates genetics algorithm (GA) with support vector machine (SVM) classifier and particle swarm algorithm for software fault prediction. The work’s strengths are its accuracy and the possibility of working in real-time and large datasets.

Reaching good results in predictions depends on the used algorithms and the data to train them. In this case, a study and evaluation of different machine-learning algorithms have been done. Table 5 shows the three main algorithms used, including a brief description for each one. Note that not all of them have been included in Section 0.5 due to poor performance or incompatibility with the data used in this paper.

Algorithm	Description
AdaBoost	<i>Adaptive Boosting</i> . It is a classification algorithm that combines multiple weak classifiers into a single “strong classifier”.
KNN	<i>K-Nearest Neighbour</i> . It is a simple classifier that works well on basic recognition problems; however, it can be slow for real-time prediction and is not robust to noisy data.
Random Forest	It is an ensemble learning method that operate by building decision trees during training and returning the class with the majority vote over all the trees in the ensemble.
SVM	<i>Support Vector Machine</i> . It works well on many classification problems, even problems in high dimensions and that are not linearly separable.

Table 5: Machine Learning algorithms studied and tested.

Authors in [35] introduced DRMS, a framework that monitors the status of parallel applications to change the number of the processes in run-time. This framework allows efficient scheduling of resources during the execution of parallel applications, and its objective is to increase the application performance and system throughput. A set of instructions is provided to monitor the status of the application. These instructions inform the Resource Coordinator (RC) when the application can be reconfigured. The data provided are collected by the run-time monitor (TC), the User Interface Coordinator (UIC) and the Resource Coordinator (RC). Then, the Job Scheduler Analyzer (JSA) generates a new configuration based on these data. The TC component deploys multiple agents (one per processor), and one of them acts as *master* to centralize the data and improve the communication with the rest of the components. The hierarchical architecture of the TC follows a similar design as other monitoring tools (including LIMITLESS).

The authors in [36] introduce a scheduling plugin for resource managers that provides a new scheduling policy based on maximizing the CPU and burst buffers utilization. The hypothesis is that the CPU utilization is not necessarily the main resource to optimize because it depends on the application characteristics and the hardware resources. Different from other methods, BBSched aims to optimize the utilization of multiple resources by providing a Pareto set for decision making, which provides a set of optimal solutions to make a scheduling decision. The authors use a multi-objective genetic algorithm over a set of applications (window-based scheduling) for obtaining results in a quick way. In this work, the authors also compare their proposal with other existing methods (scheduling policies) using two real workloads and eight synthetic workloads in a simulated environment. The results show that their proposal improves the throughput of other scheduling policies.

0.7 Conclusion

In this paper we introduce new features on LIMITLESS, a light-weight monitoring tool that was designed to monitor large-scale computing infrastructures. These features include topological-aware deployment, dynamic reconfiguration, in-situ and in-transit processing for reducing the monitor traffic, performance modelling and event detection and notification. One of the main characteristics of LIMITLESS is its integration with other platform software components like the application scheduler, CLARISSE and FlexMPI runtimes. In this paper we present novel techniques that leverage this integration for reducing the monitoring traffic. By leveraging these features, LIMITLESS is able to reduce the monitoring traffic up to 85%, and to provide application profiles based on the detected performance. Also, a new scheduling technique has been described: *fine-grain scheduling*, which is based on running applications at the same time in the same node, leveraging the phases which do not produce performance degradation in any of them. With this solution LIMITLESS can reduce the makespan on the described use cases in more than 25%. Finally, in this work

we carried out different experiments showing that LIMITLESS exhibits a good scalability and is suitable for very large-scale machines.

As a future work, we plan to monitor I/O interference and other application-related metrics for supporting multi-criteria application scheduling. We also plan to include new features to automatically detect the cluster topology with the objective of auto-deploy the monitor with an efficient layout. Finally, we want to extend this work by including more refined prediction algorithms for improving the in-transit processing algorithms, and providing an evaluation with more representative multivariate applications.

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